

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Modified urea forms evaluated in lowland rice

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The main reason for low efficiency of urea N—which generally does not exceed 50%—is due to loss of N through one or more of the well-known channels: runoff, leaching, denitrification, and volatilization. Several modified and coated urea fertilizers have been developed in recent years. We evaluated three of these, Mussorie rock phosphate-coated urea (MRPU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and large granulated urea (LGU) (6-8 mm diam), against prilled urea (PU) during 1991 and 1992 wet seasons (WS).

The soil was alluvial (Inceptisol) and sandy loam in texture with a pH of 6.8, CEC 16.3 meq/100 g soil, total N 0.05%, available P 36 ppm, and exchangeable K 1 meq/100 g soil. The water level in the field ranged from 5 to 15 cm during the crop growth period.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of variety Gayataru (CR1018) were planted during the first fortnight of July at a spacing of 15 x 15 cm. All the urea fertilizers were broadcast, applied

basally, or applied in two or three splits (see table). The N level was maintained at 60 kg/ha in the 10 treatments which were replicated three times in a randomized block design.

When the entire N dose was applied basally, MRPU and NCU were superior to PU and LGU in grain yield (see table). Single basal applications of MRPU and NCU were comparable to PU when applied in two and three splits in 1991 and three splits in 1992. A two-way split application of MRPU or NCU was not better than a single basal application. Applying LGU in two splits was comparable to applying PU in two splits. A three-way split of PU had an advantage over a two-way split in 1992 only.

N use efficiency across treatments showed a similar trend. All N applications increased grain yield significantly over the no-N control, up to 54% in 1991 and 39% in 1992.

Panicle number was highest with a basal application of MRPU in 1991; all N application treatments, except basal applications of PU and LGU, were comparable to it. In 1992, the most panicles were recorded in the conventional three-way split application of PU; all N application treatments were

comparable to it except basal application of PU and LGU. The highest panicle weight was recorded under the NCU two-way split application in 1991; comparable to it were basal applications of MRPU, LGU, and NCU and the three-way split application of PU. During 1992, highest panicle weight was recorded with PU. ■

Fertilizer scheduling and economics of varietal mixtures of rice

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Cultivating mixtures of rice varieties is a prevalent practice in many rice-growing regions. In this system, seeds of a photoperiod-insensitive variety and a photoperiod-sensitive variety are sown as a mixture in a 70-30 (wt/wt) ratio at the beginning of the wet season (WS). The varieties are successively harvested at the end of the WS and dry season (DS). We evaluated the fertilizer requirements to determine the economic productivity of the system.

The experiment was conducted during 1988-90 WS and DS. The soil at the site is lateritic loam, acidic, and of medium fertility. Aryan (Ptbl) for WS and Chettadi (local) for DS were the varieties in the mixture. The treatments were combinations of the recommended fertilizer schedule for a single variety (40-20-20 kg NPK/ha) applied in three proportions (100,75, and 50%) for the WS crop and four proportions (100,75, 50, and 25%) for the DS crop, along with a control where varieties were cropped singly in the different seasons under the recommended fertilizer schedule.

Cropping the varieties singly recorded higher grain yield than did the mixture during individual seasons as well as annually. Grain yield of the varietal mixture did not vary by season, possibly because of the substantial organic matter buildup in the system. Lowering the nutrient supply to 50% or less significantly reduced grain yield during the DS, attributable to the increased mineralization of the large

Effect of different treatments on grain yield, yield attributes, and N use efficiency in rice. CRRRI, Cuttack, India. 1991-92 WS.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Panicles/m ² (no.)		Panicle weight (g)		N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)	
	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992
Control	4.0	4.1	245	223	2.22	2.15	-	-
PU, all basal	5.3	5.2	279	258	2.24	2.25	22.2	17.3
MRPU, all basal	5.9	5.6	297	282	2.30	2.35	32.5	24.3
LGU, all basal	5.3	5.2	281	265	2.21	2.27	22.5	17.3
NCU, all basal	5.9	5.5	291	285	2.33	2.32	31.3	23.3
PU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI) ^b	5.9	5.4	292	266	2.67	2.58	31.3	21.8
MRPU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	6.1	5.7	292	283	2.69	2.50	36.0	26.8
LGU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	5.9	5.5	290	276	2.66	2.50	31.3	22.3
NCU, 2 splits (2/3 basal + 1/3 PI)	6.1	5.8	291	284	2.71	2.52	35.2	27.0
PU, 3 splits (1/2 basal + 1/4 21 DT ^c + 1/4 PI)	6.1	5.8	293	286	2.66	2.55	35.7	27.2
LSD (P=0.05)	0.3	0.2	15	20	0.20	0.27		

^aN content in fertilizers: MRPU = 36%; PU, LGU, and NCU = 46%. ^bPI = panicle initiation. ^cDT = days after transplanting.